

Theorem of 1:3 Pythagoras Cone and Prime number predictive double spirals

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Abstract : This article is a brief salute and validation of the exclusive Journal of Mathematics, JPRM, who had the wisdom and the savant to publish the preliminary papers of this author. This Theorem now is being published in Book Form later this year (The God of Papa Einstein and Isaac Newton).

Key words: double spiral of Prime number distribution, 1:3 Pythagoras cone.

Theorem :

THE THEOREM OF CREATED MATHEMATICS AT THE 1:3 PYTHAGORAS CONE

“ All numbers are naturally arranged at the created cone of 1:3 Pythagoras at a precise angle of genesis .All the prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers (multiples of prime numbers) are arranged at the half-line +3 in a very predictable double Spiral dictated by an outer spiral and a replicated inner spiral . The outer spiral which dictates the infinite arrangement by the double spiral is a template of Prime number 5 and its multiples with a set of Prime numbers at a rhythm of 10:20:10: 20 as 5, 25,35, 55, 65,85, 95, 115,125 which are multiples of 5 that translates into the inner replicated spiral of 1,5,7, 11, 13,17,19, 23, 25 These prime numbers and pseudo -prime numbers at the 1:3 cone(series A) are parallel to the natural Prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers(series B) derived from natural tri-sets of numbers at +5 of the natural numbers by the same rhythm of 10:20:10:20, as is shown by table below and there is a fixed relationship between the two series A and B of Prime numbers and Pseudo prime numbers that is mathematically and geometrically predictive by sieve of all prime number placements”

Caveat to the theorem: The natural root of mathematical numbers is -3 as shown by the series B, and that the value of prime number +5 in the created mathematics is a constant template for all Prime numbers and Pseudo-prime numbers at a rhythm of +10 as 10:20:10:20 , which rhythm is the precise same as the rhythm of multiples of prime number X5 spirals at the infinite numbers arrangement of the Pythagoras 1:3 cone

Series A (The double spiral arrangement of Prime numbers and their Multiples X5 the pseudo - Prime numbers at the cone of 1:3 Pythagoras

Numbers arrangement at 1:3 Pythagoras Cone

			16	19	22	25	28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61	64
		12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	38	42	45	48	51	54	57	60	63
5	8	11	14	17	20	23	26	29	32	35	38	41	44	47	50	53	56	59	62
+4	7	10	13	16	19	22	25	28	31	34	37	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	61
+3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60

Outer Spiral in spiral placement, multiples of 5 at 10:20:10:20:10:20, this is *infinite*

5(1)		25(5)		55(11)		85(17)		115(23)	
	10(2)		35(7)		65(13)		95(19)		125(25)

Inner spiral (precise replicate of outer spiral)

5		11		17		23		29	
	7		13		19		25		31

Outer spiral, multiples of 5 at 10:20:10:20:10, this is *infinite*

outer	spiral								
145(29)		175(35)		205(41)		235(47)		265(53)	
	155(31)		185(37)		215(43)		245(49)		
inner	spiral								
35		41		47		53		59	
	37		43		49		55		

Series B (The Natural parallel Prime number and pseudo prime number series+ 5 at tri-sets of natural numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8

-3 As the created root of all mathematics by numbers, Prime number 5 as the created template of all Prime number and pseudo-prime numbers(Mathematical Proof).

The basic Constant predictable template of Prime number 5 for all numbers In Mathematics (Proof),

Please focus in the left column and the right column and clearly on your own understand the predictability of prime number **5** at **+5** by numbers in the left column and by +10, +20, +30 +40+50 in that ascending order in increments of the value 10 in the right column . Note that: starting at base numbers of mathematics that the red numbers are comprised of solely Prime numbers , and their multiples (Pseudo prime numbers) . Clearly the root value of **5** natural numbers placement is **-3** as derived from the above table,

Table by Tri-sets of created numbers 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8----- extreme left column are the numbers at +5, and extreme right column numbers, the value at all +5 , as divided by 5 it is obvious is a constant +10, it is also obvious that the negative root is **-3**

1	2	3		3*1	=	2	+1	/5							
2*	3	4		4*2	=	3	+5	1		1	-	2	=	-1	
3	4	5		5*3	=	4	+11								
4	5	6		6*4	=	5	+19								
5	6	7		7*5	=	6	+29								
6	7	8		8*6	=	7	+41								
7*	8	9		9*7	=	8	+55	11		11	-	1	=	10	
8	9	10		10*8	=	9	+71								
9	10	11		11*9	=	10	+89								
10	11	12		12*10	=	11	+109								
11	12	13		13*11	=	12	+131								
12*	13	14		14*12	=	13	+155	31		31	-	11	=	20	
13	14	15		15*13	=	14	+181								
14	15	16		16*14	=	15	+209								
15	16	17		17*15	=	16	+239								
16	17	18		18*16	=	17	+271								
17*	18	19		19*17	=	18	+305	61		61	-	31	=	30	
18	19	20		20*18	=	19	+341								
19	20	21		21*19	=	20	+379								
...		
22*	23	24		24*20	=	23	+505	101		101	-	61	=	40	
27*	28	29		29*27	=	28	+755	151		151	-	101	=	50	
32*	33	34		34*32	=	33	+1055	211		211	-	151	=	60	
37*	38	39		39*37	=	38	+1405	281		281	-	211	=	70	

42*	43	44		44*42 =	43	+1805	361		361	-	281	=	80	
47*	48	49		49*47 =	48	+2255	451		451	-	361	=	90	
52*	53	54		54*52 =	53	+2755	551		551	-	441	=	100	
57*	58	59		59*57 =	58	+3305	661		661	-	551	=	110	
62*	63	64		64*62 =	63	+3905	781		781	-	661	=	120	
67*	68	69		69*67 =	68	+4555	911		911	-	781	=	130	
72*	73	74		74*72 =	73	+5255	1051		1051	-	911	=	140	
77*	78	79		79*77 =	78	+6005	1201		1201	-	1051	=	150	

And, as a further example for the numbers 1-19 only as in above table the gaps are 4,6,8,10,12,14,16.....(5-1=4;11-5=6;19-11=8.....)

And,

$$379-341=38(19*2)$$

$$341-305=36(18*2)$$

$$305-271=34(17*2)$$

$$271-239=32(16*2)$$

$$239-209=30(15*2)$$

$$209-181=28(14*2)$$

$$181-155=26(13*2)$$

$$155-131=24(12*2)$$

$$131-109=22(11*2)$$

$$109-89=20(10*2)$$

$$89-71=18(9*2)$$

$$71-55=16(8*2)$$

$$55-41=14(7*2)$$

$$41-29=12(6*2)$$

$$29-19=10(5*2)$$

$$19-11=8(4*2)$$

$$11-5=6(3*2)$$

$$5-1=4(2*2)$$

As these numbers further segregated as prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers in this precise series as shown above by the tables as +5, we clearly get the following fixed series with the Prime numbers/pseudo-prime numbers(in Bold) arranged clearly in the same template rhythm of series A at the cone10:20:10:20:10

Minus-3(-3+5=2)

3,2,7,12,17,22,27,32,37,42,47,52,57,62,67,72,77,82,87,92,97,102,107,112,117,122,127,132,137

As segregated,

7:17:37:47:67:77:97:107,127,137.....(10:20:10:20...by gaps),

Proof that series A and Series B are rationally parallel and predictive and will lead to full prediction and sieve of prime numbers at the oscillation of 3, 5

The two series of prime numbers/pseudo prime numbers derived by the 10:20:10:20 rhythm is as follows and is rationally predictable and parallel, and at gaps of 12 :24:12:24:12:24 as an indefinite series . Thus it is clear that as shown further in the book, *Prime numbers can be sieved and can be shown to be indefinitely **predictable and geometrically distributed at the 1:3 cone***

7	17	37	47	67	77	97	107	127	137	157	167	187	197	217
5	7	11	13	17	19	23	25	29	31	35	37	41	43	47
+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
12	24	48	60	84	96	120	132	156	168	192	204	228	240	264

Conclusion: The theorem thus clearly proves that all numbers are arranged by Inverse at a Pythagoras 1:3, generated from the point of the interface between the infinite coordinate 4, a square and a cube , and the -1 finite interface coordinate 3 which is a perfect circle/sphere The prime numbers and pseudo prime numbers are clearly placed and distributed at 1:3 cone, as was Published by JPRM , referenced below. These Spiral numbers are geometrically sieved both by numbers and geometry as outlined in the upcoming book. Mathematically there exists a dichotomy between this created mathematics and current mathematical theory of the past 1000 years. Much of this is discussed in the upcoming book

Numbers arrangement by inverse at the full 1:3 cone, sagittal orientation (spirals are shown in the half-cone arrangement below, as series A)

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